

TRANSACTIONAL DISTANCE EDUCATION IN RELATION TO LIFE AND CAREER SKILLS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. The study determined the extent of transactional distance education and the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers. This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the extent of transaction distance education was extensive while the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the transaction distance education had a strong positive correlation to the life and career skills. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of transactional distance education on life and career of public elementary school teachers: Content, Evaluation, and Technology. It was suggested that the school and its teachers may continue working in partnership with the potential stakeholders to aid learners in developing life and career skills in the workplace. Also, to enhance productivity and accountability learners may be emboldened to actively participate and focus more on their learning, especially in distance education.

KEY WORDS

1. Transaction distance education.
2. life and career skills of public-school teachers.
3. Technology.

1. Introduction

Many facets of lives have been drastically changed by the COVID-19 pandemic, which have disproportionately affected the most vulnerable sector, that is, education is no exception. According to UNICEF, more than billion children and youth were directly affected due to the imposed nationwide school closures some countries aimed to contain the spread of the disease. Likewise, the situation also prevented around 4 million students from enrolling in classes for the academic year 2020–2021, according to an official in the complete school closures. Transactional distance in the perception of psychological distance between the student and his peers, his instructor/teacher, and the learning content, has long been a prominent construct in research on distance education. transactional distance model serves as a heuristic device, a means of identifying questions for research and a very practical instrument to be used in making these

difficult instructional design decisions. Transactional managers focus on using rewards to motivate employees and boost satisfaction. They do not focus on working conditions, such as an employee's relationship with their manager, which can be critical drivers of engagement and satisfaction. Transactional distance, an influential concept in distance education, refers to the degree of psychological distance between learner and teacher. It suggests that, although separation by space and time is the most prominent characteristic of distance education, transactional distance is the actual guiding principle in distance education, influencing the process of teaching and learning. Transactional distance may also be perceived in face-to-face education, as it is a relative rather than an absolute term. The extent to which transactional distance will be perceived by the learner is a function of three variables, dialog, structure, and learner autonomy. Depending on how these variables manifest, transactional distance will be higher or lower, allowing for a typology of educational programs. Unemployment is faced by many countries as one of their problems. In the Philippines, according to the Philippine Statistics Authority the rate of unemployment was assessed. One of the factors of unemployment is the disparity in skills between what employers required and what graduates have (Abdullah, 2016). The Partnership for 21st Century Learning asserts that for students to succeed in today's social, work, and professional situations, they must develop their cognitive, content, social, and emotional competencies. The ability to navigate difficult life and work con-

texts in the globally competitive world obligates students to pay close attention to building suitable life and career skills. In the twenty-first century, these skills are crucial for both learning and employment. In the Philippines Department of Education (DepEd), the pandemic broke out just before the academic year 2019-2020 ended. The disruption was comparatively minimal, affecting the last few weeks of classes and pushing students' graduation to happen online. It was only during the academic year 2020-2021, which utilized the alternative learning delivery, that the underlying concerns came to the fore, first emphasized by anecdotal data, and later supported by surveys conducted as the pandemic storm learner autonomy identify students' life and career skills as to flexibility and adaptability; initiative and self-direction, social and cross cultural skills, productivity and accountability, and leadership and responsibility; and 3) determine if there is a significant relationship between transactional distance education elements and students' life and career skilled (Cruz, 2021). According to UNESCO (2021), in the academic year 2020-2021, nearly half of the student populations worldwide were still adversely affected by partial or learner autonomy which identify students' life and career skills as to flexibility and adaptability; initiative and self-direction, social and cross-cultural skills, productivity and accountability, and leadership and responsibility; and 3) determine if there is a significant relationship between transactional distance education elements and students' life and career skills.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. According to Briones (2021), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascertain their relationship. More to the point, Magbanua (2021) emphasizes that this method is used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses the transactional distance education of public elementary school in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This is correlational since transactional distance education and life and career skills of teachers practice of public elementary school teachers.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in seven (7) schools of Maa, Division of Davao City. The respondents were composed of 120-selected teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the transactional distance education and life and career skills of teachers in public elementary school. Random sampling technique was employed in this study. However, Langub Elementary School and Magtuod Elementary School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools are equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study adapted a questionnaire on organizational culture was patterned and adapted by the researcher from Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) as cited by Andaya (2022). He posits that in distance learning scenarios, separation between the teacher and students can “lead to

communication gaps, a psychological space of potential misunderstandings between the behaviors of instructors and those of the learners”. It was the cognitive space between teachers and students that must be crossed yet was a place of potential misunderstanding between the teacher and the learner. This is supported by Theory of Career of Super (1957) as cited Briones by (2022). This theory emphasizes that a state that in making vocational choice individuals are expressing their self-concept, or understanding of self, which evolves over time. People seek career satisfaction through work roles in which they can express themselves and further implement and develop their self-concept. Individuals apply what they learn through the exploratory process by matching their interests and abilities to occupations and applying their self-concepts to both work and life roles. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher’s preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. Validity of the instrument ensured through expert’s opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach’s Alpha with the obtained values of 0.070. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, namely: transaction distance education and life and career skills of teachers in public elementary school. Hence, the Cronbach’s value of the construct has met the minimum reliability of 0.796, it means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument’s face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items transactional with the following: planning, management, application, and evaluation. Part 2 pertained to the satisfaction of teachers namely: academic cer-

tificate, technology expertise, confidence, and District teachers were based on the following dedication creativity on teaching skills. The Five-point Likert rating scales: perceptions of the respondents among the Maa

Transactional distance education

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Transactional distance education is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Transactional distance education is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Transactional distance education is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Transactional distance education is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Transactional distance education is not evident.

Life and Career Skills of Teachers

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Life and career skills of teachers are always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Life and career skills of teachers are oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Life and career skills of teachers are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Life and career skills of teachers are rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Life and career skills of teachers are not evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The steps followed in the conduct of the study were: 1. Permission to conduct study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent them back through researcher’s email-add or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The

data were collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2020. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contam-

inated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger, viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean. It was used to determine the level of transactional distance education of public elementary school in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used

in determining the significant of transactional distance education and life and career skills of teachers of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was used to utilized to determine the significant of transactional distance education influence life and career skills of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of transactional distance education in relation to life and career skills of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of transactional distance education in terms of content, instruction, evaluation, and technology; the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers in terms of flexibility and adaptability, initiative and self-direction, productivity and accountability, and leadership and responsibility; and which of the factors of transaction distance education significantly influence the life and career skills of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Summary on the Extent of Transactional Distance Education. Presented in table 1 shows the summary on the extent of transactional distance education. The indicator with highest mean is content with a mean of (3.98), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by technology has a mean of (3.83) identified as extensive. Similarly, instruction obtained a mean

of (3.66) described as extensive. Lastly, evaluation has the least mean of (3.56) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.76) or extensive, therefore, the summary on the extent of transactional distance education was extensive as perceived by the public elementary school teachers. This means that education is recovering, but the shift in teach-

ing strategies and methods continues to present difficulties for both students and teachers, as well as exposing deficiencies and inequities in our educational systems, including a lack of access to computers and the internet for online learning, a lack of conducive and supportive environments for concentration, and a mismatch

between resources and needs. Students have difficulties understanding the lessons primarily because teaching and learning are done at a distance, plus the added hurdle of using devices and online software and the inferior telecommunication services in the country.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Transactional Distance Education

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Content	3.98	Extensive
2	Instruction	3.66	Extensive
3	Evaluation	3.56	Extensive
4	Technology	3.83	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.76	Extensive

It can be gathered from the table that content, instruction, evaluation, and technology were extensively as perceived by public elementary school teachers. Evaluation was the least among the indicators. The finding is in consonance to the idea of Alper (2020), stressing that distance education approach presented many challenges to policymakers and school principals. Teachers also had difficulty during this challenging and unexpected educational process. It is clear that this unprepared approach places an excessive burden on teachers. Dilekçi and Limon (2020), the distance education process, teachers were subjected to an excessive communication burden because

they had to communicate with managers of the provincial and district national education directorates, school principals, colleagues, parents, and students via phone, online/remote meeting, e-mail, and one-on-one online/remote communication. Moreover, Özdoğan and Berkant (2020) stressed that distance education comes with several flaws such as loss of motivation, lack of measurement and evaluation, the inadequacy of resources such as the internet and computers, inequality of opportunity in education, lack of communication and interaction, technical problems, lack of socialization and being unprepared for the distance education process.

Summary on the Extent of Life and Career. Presented in table 2 shows the summary on the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers. The indicator with highest mean is leadership and responsibility (4.18), interpreted as very extensive. It is then followed by flexibility and adaptability has a mean of (4.02) identified as extensive. Similarly, pro-

ductivity and accountability obtained a mean of (3.88) described as extensive. Lastly, initiative and self-direction has the least mean of (3.85) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.98) or extensive, therefore, the summary on the extent of life and career skills was extensively as perceived by the public elementary school teachers.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Life and Career Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Flexibility and Adaptability	4.02	Extensive
2	Initiative and Self-Direction	3.85	Extensive
3	Productivity and Accountability	3.88	Extensive
4	Leadership and Responsibility	4.18	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.98	Extensive

It can be gleaned from the table that flexibility and adaptability, initiative and self-direction, productivity and accountability, and leadership and responsibility were extensive. Initiative and self-direction was the least among the indicators of life and a career skills of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. There is, therefore, life and career skills that initiatives promoting learner-centered teaching and also awareness around child-friendly school environments are often driven, at least in part, by a concern for equity. Further, life skills encompass social attitudes, basic knowledge and practical skills. It includes but is considerably broader than vocational skills, practical skills and knowledge that lay the foundation for children to be economically productive when they enter the world of work. It is important for teachers to manage themselves to extend their craft to prepare more diverse learners for the challenge of work and life beyond school. They are challenged to provide more authentic instructional contexts and activities than traditional knowledge-based curricula (Paris, 2004) as cited by David (2017). When a teacher possesses a good management of self, he/she may in turn change student be-

havior and ultimately affect learner achievement positively (Manzano, 2018).

Significant Relationship Between Transactional Distance Education and Life Career Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between transactional distance education and life and career skills of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Based on the analysis, the overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.749. This means that there is a strong significant positive correlation between the transactional distance education and life career skills of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its set null hypothesis. Furthermore, the analysis depicts that an increasing manifestations of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers leads to an increase of their life and career skills. Specifically, the analysis highlighted the individual relationship of each indicator of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers and their life and career skills.

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Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Transactional Distance Education and Life & Career Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Life & Career Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers	Transactional Distance Education		
	r	p-value	decision
Content	0.671	0.000	Reject
Instruction	0.510	0.000	Reject
Evaluation	0.390	0.000	Reject
Technology	0.655	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.749	0.000	Reject

ementary school teachers leads to an increase of their life and career skills. Specifically, the analysis in Table 4 highlighted the individual relationship of each indicator of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers and their life and career skills. Based on the analysis, the Content indicator of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers ranked as the top indicator garnering a strong significant positive correlation with their life career skills which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.671. This was followed by the Technology indicator of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers obtaining a strong significant positive correlation with their life career skills which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.655. Third, is the Instruction indicator of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers obtaining a moderate significant positive correlation with their life and career skills which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.510. Lastly, is the Evaluation indicator of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers garnering a weak significant positive correlation with their life career skills which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.390. In addition, all of the indicators of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers show direct positive relationship to their life career skills. This means that as the following dis-

cussed indicators were increasingly manifesting by the public elementary school teachers then, their life and career skills will also increase.

Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Transactional Distance Education on the Life and Career Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers

As shown in the table 4, the overall analysis obtained p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 44.918 stating that there is a significant influence of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers on their life career skills in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This also implies that the regression model used in the analysis of the study is useful and that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influences. In addition, the regression analysis of the study showed three (3) out of the four (4) indicators of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers significantly influence their life career skills in Maa District, Division of Davao City. These transactional distance education indicators of public elementary school teachers were the Content indicator which obtained a t-value equal to 6.401 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Technology indicator which obtained a t-value equal to 4.368 and a p-value equal to 0.000, and the Evaluation indicator which obtained a t-value equal to 2.240 and a p-value equal to 0.015.

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Transactional Distance Education on the Life & Career Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Life & Career Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers Transactional Distance Education	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	β	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho
Constant	1.138	.233		4.879	.000	
Content	.317	.050	.436	6.401	.000	Reject
Instruction	.087	.058	.114	1.517	.132	Reject
Evaluation	.126	.056	.142	2.240	.027	Reject
Technology	.242	.055	.333	4.368	.000	Reject

With this findings, the set null hypothesis of this study that there are no indicators of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers that significantly influence their life and career skills in Maa District, Division of Davao City is rejected. On the other hand, the Instruction indicator of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers does not significantly influence their life and career skills in Maa District, Division of Davao City since it obtained a t-value equal to 1.517 and a p-value equal to 0.181. Significantly, the established results of the regression

analysis garnered an R2 equal to 0.610. This means that there are 61 percent ascribed to the significance influence of transactional distance education of public elementary school teachers that significantly influence their life and career skills in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Thus, the other 39 percent is ascribed to the other indicators not stipulated in the study. Particularly, these indicators could be included to determine that they might have stipulated influence to the life and career skills of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of transactional distance education and the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of transactional distance education in terms of content, instruction, evaluation, and technology. Moreover, this identified the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers in terms flexibility and adaptability, initiative and self-direction, productivity and accountability, and leadership and re-

sponsibility. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of transactional distance education and the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers. Using the non-experimental research, the extent of transactional distance education and life and career skills of public elementary school teachers was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the Theory of Moore (1997) as cited by Andaya (2022)

and Theory of Career (1957) as cited by Briones (2022) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of transactional distance education in terms of content, instruction, evaluation, and technology was extensive. Similarly, the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers in terms of flexibility and adaptability, initiative and self-direction, productivity and accountability, and leadership and responsibility was extensive which means that it was sometimes manifested while in terms of transactional distance education which also extensive. Hence, the extent of life and career skills as demonstrated by public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City was extensive. Finally, indicators of transactional distance education such content, technology, and evaluation have significant influence of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The extent of transactional distance education was extensive. The extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers was also extensive. There was a strong positive correlation in the extent of transactional

distance education and the extent of life and career skills of public elementary school teachers based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the set null hypothesis of this study that there are no indicators of the teachers' transactional distance education significantly influence life and career skills of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City is rejected.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: The school and its teachers may continue working in partnership with the potential stakeholders to aid learners in developing life and career skills in the workplace. Also, to enhance productivity and accountability learners may be emboldened to actively participate and focus more on their learning, especially in distance education. Teachers may be encouraged to continue using and enhancing their current approaches and methods since it is observed that the structure, dialogue, and autonomy of learners in their current educational setup aid in the development of skills needed by the 21st century learners. Future Researchers may use the findings of this as springboard to conduct a study with a similar subject but with a larger scope to explore other dimension of the study.

5. References

- Allen, I. and Seaman, J. (2016). *Entering the mainstream: The quality and extent of online education in the United States, 2003 and 2004*. Needham, MA: The Sloan Consortium. Retrieved from [http://www.educause.edu/Resources/Entering the Mainstream the Quality/153420](http://www.educause.edu/Resources/Entering%20the%20Mainstream%20the%20Quality/153420)
- Alper, A. (2020). Pandemi sürecinde k-12 düzeyinde uzaktan eğitim: durum çalışması. *Milli Eğitim Dergisi*, 49(1), 45-67.
- Andaya, J. (2022). Transactional distance education and the life and career Skills of technical-vocational-livelihood students. jesica.andaya@gmail.com1, edna.briones@lspu.edu.ph2 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2219-45151> Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo, Laguna, Philippines DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54476/ioer-imrj/90668>.
- Anderson, T. (2018). Modes of interaction in distance education: Recent developments and research questions. In M. G. Moore & W. G. Anderson (Eds.), *Handbook of Distance Education* (pp. 129–144). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum
- Bastiaens, F. (2017). Moore's theory of transactional distance-instructional design models, theories, methods <https://k3hamilton.Com>. <https://k3hamilton.com/LTech/transactional>
- Bischoff, W. et al. (2019). Transactional distance, interactive television, and electronic mail communication in graduate public health and nursing courses: Implications for professional education (Unpublished doctoral thesis), University of Hawaii. UMI NO: AAT 9334909
- Bennis, W. (2019). Transformative power and leadership," in *Leadership and Organizational Culture*, eds T. J. Sergiovanni and J. E. Corbally (University of Illinois Press), 64–71.
- Boyd, M. (2012). Planning and realigning a lesson in response to student contributions *The Elementary School Journal*
- Brown, L. (2017). Instructor usage of learning management systems utilizing a technology acceptance model. [Doctoral dissertation, Montana State University]. <https://scholarworks.montana.edu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/1/14062/BrownL1217.pdf?sequence=4&isAllowed=y>
- Corpuz., B. (2018). *Principles of teaching* Quezon City; Lorimar Publishing Inc.

- Colorado, J. (2019). Student demographics and success in online learning environments. *Emporia State Research Studies*, 46(1), 4-10. Retrieved from <http://academic.emporia.edu/esrs/vol46/colorado.pdf>, J.
- Chen, Y. (2021). Transactional distance in World Wide Web learning environments. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 55(4), 327–338.
- Collie, R.J., & Martin, A.J. (2016). Adaptability: An important capacity for effective teachers. *Educational Practice and Theory*, 38, 27-39 DOI10.7459/ept/38.1.03.
- Day, et. al., (2018). Leadership development: a review in context. *Leadersh. Q*, 11, 581–613. doi: 10.1016/S1048-9843(00)00061
- Department of Education. (2021). Policy guidelines on the k to 12 basic education program. Philippines department of education. [HTTPs://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/DO_s2019_021.pdf](https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/DO_s2019_021.pdf)
- Dilekçi, Ü., & Limon, İ. (2020). COVID-19 salgını bağlamında öğretmenlerin algıladıkları “aşırı iletişim yükü” düzeyi. *Milli Eğitim Dergisi*, 49(1), 231-252
- Downs, J. (2016). Exploring blended learning: A case study of adult learners using a learning management system in face-to-face classes. [Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University]. <https://apnts.whdl.org/exploring-blended-learning-case-study-adult-learners-using-learningmanagement-system-face-face>
- Duckworth, et. al., (2019). Coronavirus (COVID-19) and online learning in higher institutions of education: A survey of the perceptions of Ghanaian international students in China. *Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies*, 10(3), e202018. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ojcm/8286>
- Gaba, et. al., (2021). Factors influencing the preference of distance learners to study through online during COVID-19 pandemic. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 16(1), 194-206. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4965925>
- Garrison, R. (2020). Theoretical challenges for distance education in the 21st century: A shift from structural to transactional issues. *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 1(1), 1–17. Retrieved from www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/download/2/22

- Goel, V. (2020). Transactional distance and student satisfaction in a postgraduate distance learning program. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 48 62. <https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.762023>
- Gope, et. al. (2021). Higher education in India: Challenges and opportunities of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 16(1),54-73. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4643552>
- Gronn, P. (2020). Distributed properties: A new architecture for leadership. *Educational Management Administration Leadership*, 28(3), 317-338.
- Halupa, Colleen. (2016). Risks: The impact of online learning and technology on student physical, mental, emotional, and social health. 6305-6314. [10.21125/iceri.2016.0044](https://doi.org/10.21125/iceri.2016.0044).
- Hillman, (2020). A new method for analyzing patterns of interaction. *The American Journal of Distance Education*, 13(2), 37–47.
- Heckhausen, R. (2019). A motivational theory of life-span development. *Psychological Review*, 117(1), 32-60. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/a0017668>
- Howard, S., & Johnson, B. (2019). Resilient and non-resilient behavior in adolescents. In A.
- Henman, (2017). Leadership: Theories and controversies. Retrieved from www.henmanperformancegroup.com
- Jordan, S. (2018). Initial trends in enrolment and completion of massive open online courses. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 15(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v15i1.1651>
- Jung, I. (2019). Building a theoretical framework of Web-based instruction in the context of distance education. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 32(5), 525–534.
- Kearsley, G. (2018). Distance education: A systems review. Belmont: Wadsworth Publishing Company.
- Kim, J. (2020). Teaching and learning after COVID-19. Inside higher education. <https://www.insidehighered.com/digital-learning/blogs/learning-innovation/teaching-and-learning-after-covid-19>
- Liem, G. A. D., & Martin, A. J. (2015). Young people's responses to environmental issues: Exploring the roles of adaptability and personality. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 79, 91-97. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2015.02.003>

- Lin, C.-P., Huang, H.-T., and Huang, T. Y. (2020). The effects of responsible leadership and knowledge sharing on job performance among knowledge workers. *Person. Rev.* 49, 1879–1896. doi: 10.1108/pr-12-2018-0527
- Lumpkin, A. (2018). Teachers as role models teaching character and moral virtues. *J. Phys. Educ. Recreat. Dance* 79, 45–50. doi:10.1080/07303084.2008.10598134
- Martin, R. (2019). Teacher efficacy in student engagement, instructional management, student stressors, and burnout: a theoretical model using in-class variables to predict teachers' intent-to-leave. *Teach. Teach. Educ.* 28, 546–559. doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2011.12.003
- Miska, C., and Mendenhall, M. E. (2018). Responsible leadership: a mapping of extant research and future directions. *J. Bus. Ethics* 148, 117–134. doi: 10.1007/s10551-015-2999-0
- Moore, M. (1997). Theory of transactional distance. In D. Keegan (Ed.), *Theoretical principles of distance education* (pp. 22–38). New York: Routledge.
- Murphy, K. & Collins, M. (2017). Development of communication conventions in instructional electronic chats. *Journal of Distance Education*, 72(1/2), 177-200.
- Muijs, D. & Harris, A. (2018). Teacher leadership-Improvement through empowerment. *Educational Management & Administration*, 31(4), 437-448
- O'Connell, D. J., McNeely, E., & Hall, D. T. (2008). Unpacking personal adaptability at work. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 14(3), 248-259. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1071791907311005>
- Özdoğan, A. Ç., & Berkant, H. G. (2020). Covid-19 pandemi dönemindeki uzaktan eğitime ilişkin paydaş görüşlerinin incelenmesi. *Milli Eğitim Dergisi*, 49(1), 13-43.
- Parson, A. (2019). Adaptive teaching in literacy instruction: Case studies of two teachers. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 44(2), 149-170. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1086296X12440261>
- Peña, C. D. (2018). *Developing Professionally*. Sun Star Pampanga.
- Purvanova, R. and Bono, J. (2019). Transformational leadership in context: face-to-face and virtual teams. *Leadership Q* 20, 343–357. doi: 10.1016/j.leaqua.2009.03.004

- Raja, R., & Nagasubramani, P. C. (2018). Impact of modern technology in education. *Journal of Applied and Advanced Research*, S33–S35. <https://doi.org/10.21839/jaar.2018.v3is1.165>
- Reagan, et. al. (2019). Place matters: Review of the literature on rural teacher education *Teaching And Teacher Education: An International Journal of Research and Studies*
- Sims, R. & Brinkman, J. (2019). Leaders as moral role models: the case of John Gutfreund at Salomon brothers. *J. Bus. Ethic*doi10.1023/A:1013826126058
- Setyawan, F. et. al., (2020). Effects of the Google meet assisted method of learning on building student knowledge and learning outcomes. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(9), 3924 - 3936. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080901>
- Terry, P. (2017). Empowering teachers as leaders. *National Forum Journals*. Retrieved from <http://www.nationalforum.com/Electronic%20Journal%20Volumes/Terry,%20paul%20M.%20Empowering>
- Tinungki , M & Nurwahyu, L. (2020). The implementation of Google classroom as the e-learning platform for teaching Non-Parametric Statistics during COVID19 Pandemic in Indonesia. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(4), 5793-5803. <http://sersc.org/journals/index.php/IJAST/article/view/27089>
- Tomasik, M. 2018). Is it adaptive to disengage from demands of social change? Adjustment to developmental barriers in opportunity-deprived regions. *Motivation and Emotion*, 34(4), 384-398. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11031-010-9177-6>
- Ulla, M. B., Barrera, K. B., & Acompañado, M. M. (2017). Philippine Classroom Teachers as Researchers: Teachers' Perceptions, Motivations, and Challenges. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 42(11). <http://ro.ecu.edu.au/ajte/vol>.
- UNESCO. (2021, November 7). *Education: From disruption to recovery*. Unesco.Org. <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
- SDM 176 s. 2020. (2020). Division Research Calendar SY 2020-2021. Department of Education, Schools of Division of San Jose del Monte City.

- Wardynski, D. J. (2019, November 7). What are the effects of technology on human interaction? Brainspire. <https://www.brainspire.com/blog/whatare-the-effects-of-technology-on-humaninteraction#:~:text=Increased%20isolation%2C%20reduced%20social%20interaction,wall%20between%20many%20people%20globally.>
- Willging, S. (2018). Factors that influence students' decision to dropout of online courses. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 13(3), 115-127.
- Windchill, K. (2019). Explaining social presence and the quality of online learning with the SIPS model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 72, 479-487
- Xiao, J. (2021). Decoding new normal in education for the post-COVID-19 world: Beyond the digital solution. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 16(1), 141-155. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818369>
- Zhang, A. (2019). Transactional distance in web-based college learning environments: Towards measurement and theory construction (Doctoral thesis). Richmond: Virginia Commonwealth University. UMI No: AAT 3082019